

Synthesis of novel 5-phenylselenenyl pyrimidine analogs

N. Jeelan Basha, CH Uendar Reddy and N. M. Goudgaon*

Department of Studies and Research in Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga-585 106, Karnataka, India

E-mail : naganna_g@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 25 January 2008, revised 9 January 2009, accepted 26 February 2009

Abstract : 5-Phenylselenenyl-4-substituted-2-benzylthiopyrimidine analogs were prepared efficiently in four steps. Reaction of 2-thiouracil with benzyl chloride in presence of base furnishes 2-benzylthio uracil, which on reaction with phenylselenenyl chloride in pyridine under anhydrous conditions yielded 5-phenylselenenyl-2-benzylthio uracil. Chlorination of 5-phenylselenenyl-2-benzylthio uracil with excess POCl₃ under reflux furnishes 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine. Aromatic nucleophilic substitution reaction of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine with oxygen nucleophiles like sodium ethoxide, sodium benzyolate and nitrogen nucleophiles like aliphatic primary amines, substituted aromatic primary amines furnished the target compounds in 48–80% yield. 5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(substitutedbenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidines were prepared in 60–75% yield, by the reaction of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-(hydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine with various aromatic aldehydes.

Keywords : 5-Phenylselenenyl pyrimidine, uracil, synthesis.

Introduction

Compared to sulfur compounds, the corresponding selenium analogs appear to be much more active in cancer prevention¹. A number of selenium compounds, such as sodium selenite, sodium selenate and lesser extent selenocystine and selenomethionine, have been used successfully as dietary supplements for suppression of tumor growth in rodents². Several nucleosides containing selenium were found to have biological activity^{3–9}. 5-Hydro-seleno-2'-deoxyuridylate is a potent inhibitor of *L. casei* thymidylate synthase³. This compound was synthesized as an analogue of 5-mercapto-2'-deoxyuridylate, a known inhibitor of this enzyme¹⁰.

In continuation of literature search relating to the importance of selenium in biologically active molecules containing 1,2,3-selenodiazole moieties were well known for their pharmacological properties like potential antimicrobial^{11,12}, antihemostatic¹³ and insecticidal¹⁴. Phenylselenenyl substituted pyrimidines were synthesized and evaluated for the inhibition of enzymes involved in pyrimidine metabolism^{15–23} such as dihydrouracil dehydrogenase (DHUase), orotate phosphoribosyl transferase (OPRTase), thymidine phosphorylase (Thdpase) and uridine phosphorylase (Urdpase). Here, we report a facile methodology for the synthesis of various 5-phenylselenenyl-4-substituted-2-benzylthiopyrimidines starting from 2-thiouracil.

Results and discussion

2-Thiouracil 1 was reacted with benzyl chloride in presence of base furnished 2-benzylthio uracil 2 in 86% yield having m.p. 186–187 °C as a white crystalline solid. The reaction of compound 2 with phenylselenenyl chloride in dry pyridine under anhydrous condition at 60–65 °C for 24 h furnished the expected compound 5-phenylselenenyl-2-benzylthio uracil 3 in 65% yield as a white crystalline solid having m.p. 175–177 °C. The IR spectrum of compound 3 shows characteristic absorptions of NH at 3180, C=O at 1636 and -C=N at 1591 cm⁻¹ respectively. Further, the structure of compound 3 was confirmed by the ¹H NMR spectrum and the characteristic signals are at δ 12.4 (1H, s, NH), 7.79 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.53–7.26 (10H, m, C₆H₅), 4.36 (2H, s, SCH₂Ph). The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound 3 indicates the phenylselenenyl group was attached to the C₅-position of the pyrimidine ring. A significant deshielding effect of H-6 was caused by the presence of a selenium substituent at the C₅-position of the pyrimidine ring. In this case the reaction may proceed via the direct addition of phenylselenenyl chloride to the 5,6-double bond followed by elimination of HCl by pyridine. Compound 3 on subjected to chlorination with POCl₃ yielded 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine 4 as a brown crystalline solid in 90% yield, having m.p. 59–60 °C. The struc-

tural assignment of the compound **4** was based on the spectral data. IR spectrum of compound **4** shows the absence of NH and C=O absorptions at 3180, 1636 cm^{-1} respectively, while it shows the presence of C-Cl absorption at 735 cm^{-1} . By the analysis of IR spectrum of compound **4**, we concluded that chlorination has been taken place with POCl_3 . Further confirmation of the structure of compound **4** was based on the ^1H NMR spectrum. The spectrum exhibits the characteristic signals at δ 8.0 (1H,

s, C_6H), 7.6–7.1 (10H, m, C_6H_5), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph). Additional confirmation is the absence of NH peak at δ 12.4 due to the aromatization of 5-phenylselenenyl-2-benzylthiouracil **3** to 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine **4**.

The title compounds **5a** and **5b** were obtained by the reaction of **4** with oxygen nucleophiles such as sodium ethoxide and sodium benzylate in dry toluene under N_2 atmosphere for overnight at room temperature, via the

Scheme 1

aromatic nucleophilic substitution reaction. Compound **5b** was obtained in 65% yield, having m.p. 59–60 °C as a brown crystalline solid. The ^1H NMR signals are at δ 8.3 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.55–7.23 (15H, m, C_6H_5), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph) and 3.36 (2H, s, OCH_2Ph). Further the structure of compound **5b** was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : C, 62.32; H, 4.31; N, 6.05. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{OSse}$: C, 62.33; H, 4.32; N, 6.06%).

The formation of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-amino-2-benzylthiopyrimidines **5c-h** by the reaction of compound **4** with various nitrogen nucleophiles such as substituted aromatic primary amines in methanol at refluxing temperature with catalytic amount of pyridine via the aromatic nucleophilic substitution reaction. Compound **5c** was obtained in 63% yield, as a semisolid. The IR spectrum of compound **5c** shows the presence of NH absorption at 3337 cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR spectrum of **5c** shows the proton signals at δ 8.4 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6 (1H, s, NH), 7.4–6.9 (14H, m, ArH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph), 2.2 (3H, s, CH_3). ^{13}C NMR shift assignments of CH_3 carbon at 30 ppm, SCH_2 carbon at 36 ppm, C_5 carbon of pyrimidine ring at 122 ppm, aromatic carbon signals at 127–137 ppm and C_2 , C_4 and C_6 carbons of pyrimidine ring at 159 ppm, 163 ppm and 173 ppm respectively. Compound **5d** was obtained in 68% yield, as a semisolid. The IR spectrum of compound **5d** shows the presence of NH absorption at 3350, C-O-C absorption at 1185. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **5d** shows the proton signals at δ 8.4 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6–7.0 (14H, m, ArH), 6.2 (1H, s, NH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph), 4.2 (3H, s, OCH_3). Further con-

firmation of compound **5d** is based on the mass spectral data, the molecular ion peak at m/z 480 (M^+ , 80%), fragmented ion peaks are at 357 (5%), 324 (100%), 200 (10%) and 91.

Reaction of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-(hydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine **5i** with various aromatic aldehydes in presence of acid catalyst and methanol as solvent furnishes 5-phenylselenenyl-4-(substitutedbenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidines **5j-m** upon reflux for 4 h. Compound **5j** was obtained in 75% yield, m.p. 110–112 °C. The IR spectrum of compound **5j** shows the presence of NH absorption at 3355, C=N absorption at 1597 and C-O-C absorption at 1253 cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR spectrum of **5j** shows the proton signals at δ 8.24 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.7–6.8 (16H, m, ArH, 1 N=CH, 1 NH), 4.4 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3). Further confirmation of compound **5j** is based on the mass spectral data, the molecular ion peak at m/z 505 (M^+ , 90%), fragmented ion peaks are at 429 (95%), 414 (100%).

Experimental

2-Thiouracil was purchased from Hi-Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai (India), benzyl chloride, POCl_3 , benzyl alcohol, anilines and aldehydes were purchased from SISCO Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai (India). All the solvents used were of analytical grade or were purified according to standard procedures. Melting points were determined by using a Thomas-Hoover melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr disc were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Spectrum-one

Table 1. Synthesis of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-substituted-2-benzylthiopyrimidines (**5a-m**)

Compd.	R	R'	R''	M.p. ^a (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
5a	Et	–	–	Semi-solid	58
5b	CH_2Ph	–	–	59–60	65
5c	–	CH_3	–	Semi-solid	63
5d	–	OCH_3	–	Semi-solid	68
5e	–	Cl	–	Semi-solid	52
5f	–	Br	–	Semi-solid	50
5g	–	NO_2	–	Semi-solid	48
5h	–	–	–	Semi-solid	58
5i	–	–	–	140–141	80
5j	–	–	OCH_3	110–111	75
5k	–	–	$\text{OCH}_3(p)$, $\text{OH}(m)$	121–122	70
5l	–	–	$\text{OH}(o)$	153–154	60
5m	–	–	$\text{Cl}(p)$	190–191	72

^aMelting points are uncorrected. ^bYield refers to purified product.

FT IR spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) and ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ and/or CDCl_3 on amx 400, 400 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift in δ or ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102 Mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon (6 kv, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel 'G' plates obtained from Whatman Inc, and a fluorescent indicator. 2-Benzylthiouracil **2** was prepared by following the known literature method²⁴.

Procedure for the preparation of 5-phenylselenenyl-2-benzylthio uracil (3) :

Phenylselenenyl chloride (0.006 mol) was dissolved in dry pyridine (15 ml) and then 2-benzylthio uracil (0.006 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 60–65 °C for 24 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and then concentrated under vacuum to remove pyridine. The residue was co-evaporated with benzene and EtOH (20 : 10 ml). The residue was loaded on silica gel column and eluted with CHCl_3 to remove diphenyldiselenide. The product was then obtained on elution with CHCl_3 : MeOH (95 : 5) and TLC pure fractions were pooled and concentrated. Yield : 1.45 g (65%), m.p. 175–177 °C; IR (KBr) : 3180 (NH), 1636 (C=O), 1591 cm^{-1} (C=N-); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 12.4 (1H, s, NH), 7.79 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.53–7.26 (10H, m, C_6H_5), 4.36 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph) (Found : C, 54.82; H, 3.75; N, 7.51. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{OSSe}$: C, 54.83; H, 3.76; N, 7.52%).

Procedure for the preparation of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (4) :

A mixture of 5-phenylselenenyl-2-benzylthio uracil (0.01 mol) and POCl_3 (0.1 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess POCl_3 was removed under reduced pressure, and the mixture was treated with ice-cold water. The separated solid was extracted with ether and washed with aq. NaHCO_3 (5%) solution. Ether layer was collected and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and after solvent evaporation yielded the title compound **4**, which is recrystallized from EtOH. Yield : 3.51 g (90%), m.p. 59–60 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 8.0 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6–7.1 (10H, m, C_6H_5), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph) (Found : C, 52.28; H, 3.30; N, 7.15. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{SSeCl}$: C, 52.30; H, 3.33; N, 7.17%).

Procedure for the preparation of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-ethoxy-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5a) :

Small pieces of sodium metal (0.001 mol) were added

in 6 ml of dry ethanol with stirring in an inert atmosphere. After the sodium metal was dissolved in ethanol, thick viscous sodium ethoxide was formed. A solution of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine **4** (0.001 mol) in anhydrous toluene (20 ml) was slowly added to sodium ethoxide and stirred overnight. Precipitate of sodium chloride formed during the reaction was removed by filtration and the solid was washed with toluene. The filtrate was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was recrystallized from spirit to furnish the title compound **5a** in the form of semisolid. Yield : 0.23 g (58%); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 8.3 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.8–7.2 (10H, m, C_6H_5), 4.2 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph), 3.7 (2H, q, OCH_2), 1.2 (3H, t, CH_3) (Found : C, 56.98; H, 4.40; N, 7.00. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{OSSe}$: C, 57.00; H, 4.50; N, 7.01%).

Procedure for the preparation of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-benzoyloxy-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5b) :

A stirred solution of benzyl alcohol (0.002 mol) was treated with 60% w/w NaH in oil (0.002 mol) under nitrogen atmosphere and the mixture was warmed to 55–60 °C for 30 min to facilitate the formation of sodium salt. After all the NaH had reacted, the suspension was cooled and 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine **4** (0.002 mol) in anhydrous toluene (20 ml) was slowly added maintaining the temperature at 25–30 °C. After stirring overnight, the precipitate of sodium chloride formed during the reaction was removed by filtration and the solid was washed with toluene. The filtrate was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was recrystallized from EtOH to give pure title compound **5b**. Yield : 0.6 g (65%); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 8.3 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.55–7.23 (15H, m, C_6H_5), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2Ph), 3.36 (2H, s, OCH_2Ph) (Found : C, 62.32; H, 4.31; N, 6.05. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{OSSe}$: C, 62.33; H, 4.32; N, 6.06%).

General procedure for the preparation of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-anilino-2-benzylthiopyrimidines (5c-i) :

To a solution of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-chloro-2-benzylthiopyrimidine **4** (0.001 mol) in methanol (20 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml), appropriate aromatic primary amine (0.001 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath. The reaction solution was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue was triturated with a little crushed ice and the aqueous layer was neutralized with 0.1 N HCl, extracted with ether (3 \times 25 ml), dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and the ether was evaporated to get the desired compounds **5c-i**.

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-methylanilino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5c) : Yield : 0.29 g (63%); IR : 3337 cm^{-1} (NH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.4 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6 (1H, s, NH), 7.4–6.9 (14H, m, ArH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2), 2.2 (3H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR : 30 (CH_3), 36 (SCH_2), 122 (C_5), 127–137 (ArC), 159 (C_2), 163 (C_4), 173 (C_6) (Found : C, 60.40; H, 4.79; N, 9.60. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{SSe}$: C, 60.41; H, 4.80; N, 9.61%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-methoxyanilino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5d) : Yield : 0.32 g (68%); IR : 3350 (NH), 1185 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.3 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6–7.0 (14H, m, ArH), 6.2 (1H, s, NH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2), 4.25 (3H, s, OCH_3). Mass : 480 (M^+ , 80%), 357, 324, 200, 91 (Found : C, 58.26; H, 4.62; N, 9.26. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{OSSe}$: C, 58.27; H, 4.63; N, 9.27%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-chloroanilino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5e) : Yield : 0.25 g (52%); IR : 3440 (NH), 733 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.4 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.9 (1H, s, NH), 7.5–7.0 (14H, m, ArH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2); ^{13}C NMR : 36 (SCH_2), 120 (C_5), 127–137 (ArC), 158 (C_2), 163 (C_4), 173 (C_6) (Found : C, 55.13; H, 3.92; N, 9.18. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{ClSSe}$: C, 55.14; H, 3.93; N, 9.19%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-bromoanilino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5f) : Yield : 0.26 g (50%); IR : 3349 (NH), 735 cm^{-1} (C-Br); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.4 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.9 (1H, s, NH), 7.6–7.0 (14H, m, ArH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2) (Found : C, 50.18; H, 3.57; N, 8.35. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{BrSSe}$: C, 50.19; H, 3.58; N, 8.36%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-nitroanilino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5g) : Yield : 0.237 g (48%); IR : 3377 (NH), 1464 cm^{-1} (N=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.0 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.9 (1H, s, NH), 7.6–7.0 (14H, m, ArH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2) (Found : C, 53.83; H, 3.83; N, 11.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SSe}$: C, 53.84; H, 3.84; N, 11.96%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(2-naphthylamino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5h) : Yield : 0.28 g (58%); IR : 3439 cm^{-1} (NH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.0 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6–7.2 (17H, m, ArH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2), 4.25 (1H, s, NH) (Found : C, 65.32; H, 4.02; N, 8.45. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{SSe}$: C, 65.33; H, 4.03; N, 8.46%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(hydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5i) : Yield : 0.309 g (80%); IR : 3384, 3293 cm^{-1} (NH/NH); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.29 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.4–7.2 (10H, m, ArH), 6.89 (1H, s, NH), 4.4 (2H, s, SCH_2), 3.48 (2H, s, NH_2). Mass : m/z 388 (M^+ , 100%),

374 (5%), 359 (10%), 203 (2%) (Found : C, 52.70; H, 4.15; N, 14.45. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{SSe}$: C, 52.71; H, 4.16; N, 14.46%).

General procedure for the preparation of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-(substitutedbenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidines (5j-m) :

To a solution of 5-phenylselenenyl-4-(hydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine **5i** (0.001 mol) in methanol (20 ml) and 4–5 drops of concentrated HCl, appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid separated was filtrated and recrystallized from alcohol to get the desired compounds **5j-m**.

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-methoxybenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5j) : Yield : 0.379 g (75%); IR : 3355 (NH), 1597 (C=N), 1253 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.24 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.7–6.8 (16H, m, 14 ArH, 1 N=CH, 1 NH), 4.4 (2H, s, SCH_2), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3). Mass : m/z 505 (M^+ , 90%), 429 (95%), 414 (100%) (Found : C, 59.39; H, 4.37; N, 11.05. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OSSe}$: C, 59.40; H, 4.39; N, 11.08%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-methoxy-3-hydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5k) : Yield : 0.364 g (70%); IR : 3570 (OH), 3390 (NH), 1563 (C=N), 1282 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.03 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.4–6.7 (16H, m, 13 ArH, 1 N=CH, 1 OH, 1 NH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3). Mass : m/z 522 (M^+ , 100%), 493 (2%), 482 (1%) (Found : C, 57.55; H, 4.24; N, 10.72. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{SSe}$: C, 57.58; H, 4.25; N, 10.74%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5l) : Yield : 0.29 g (60%); IR : 3444 (OH), 3145 (NH), 1597 cm^{-1} (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.6 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.6–6.7 (17H, m, 14 ArH, 1 N=CH, 1 NH, 1 OH), 4.4 (2H, s, SCH_2). Mass : m/z 491 (M^+ , 100%), 415 (20%), 402 (20%) (Found : C, 58.63; H, 4.08; N, 11.38. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{OSSe}$: C, 58.65; H, 4.10; N, 11.40%).

5-Phenylselenenyl-4-(4-chlorobenzylidenehydrazino)-2-benzylthiopyrimidine (5m) : Yield : 0.36 g (72%); IR : 3422 (NH), 1592 cm^{-1} (C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.6 (1H, s, C_6H), 8.2–7.2 (16H, m, 14 ArH, 1 N=CH, 1 NH), 4.3 (2H, s, SCH_2). Mass : m/z 511 (M^+ , 100%), 387 (2%), 277 (2%) (Found : C, 58.61; H, 3.75; N, 10.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{ClSSe}$: C, 55.63; H, 3.76; N, 10.99%).

References

1. H. J. Thompson, A. Wilson, J. Lu, M. Singh, C. Jiang, P. Upadhyaya, E. Bayoumy and C. Ip, *Carcinogenesis*, 1994, **15**, 183.
2. S. Vadhanavikit, C. Ip and H. E. Ganther, *Xenobiotica*, 1993, **23**, 731.
3. S. Choi, T. I. Kalman and T. J. Bardos, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1979, **22**, 618.
4. J. J. Kirsi, J. A. North, P. A. McKernan, B. K. Murray, P. G. Canonico, J. W. Huggins, P. C. Srivasta and R. K. Robins, *Antimicro. Agents Chemother.*, 1983, **24**, 351.
5. G. H. Milne and L. B. Townsend, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1972, **22**, 618.
6. G. H. Milne and L. B. Townsend, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 745.
7. H. G. Mautner, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5292.
8. H. G. Mautner, S. H. Chu, J. J. Jaffe and A. C. Sartorelli, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 36.
9. J. G. Liehr, C. L. Weise, P. F. Crain, G. H. Milne, D. E. Wise, L. B. Townsend and J. A. McCloskey, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1979, **16**, 1263.
10. T. I. Kalman and T. J. Bardos, *Mol. Pharmacol.*, 1970, **6**, 621.
11. S. Hussein, B. El-Kashef, El-Bayoumy and I. A. Talaat, *Egypt J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1986, **27**, 27.
12. S. El-Bahaie, M. G. Assy and M. M. Hassanien, *Pharmazie*, 1990, **45**, 791.
13. B. M. Patil, B. V. Badami and G. S. Puranik, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1994, **3**, 193.
14. V. Padmavathi, R. P. Sumathi and A. Padmaja, *J. Ecobiol.*, 2002, **14**, 9.
15. J. B. Bher, T. Gourlain, A. Helimi and G. Guillerm, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, **13**, 1713.
16. J. G. Niedzwicki, M. H. el Kouni, S. H. Chu and S. Cha, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1981, **30**, 2097.
17. J. G. Niedzwicki, S. H. Chu, M. H. el Kouni, E. C. Rowe and S. Cha, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1982, **31**, 1857.
18. J. G. Niedzwicki, M. H. el Kouni, S. H. Chu and S. Cha, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1983, **32**, 399.
19. M. H. el Kouni, F. N. M. Naguib, S. H. Chu, S. Cha, T. Ueda, G. Gosselin, J. L. Imbach, Y. F. Shealy and B. A. Otter, *Mol. Pharmacol.*, 1988, **34**, 104.
20. F. N. M. Naguib, M. H. el Kouni, S. H. Chu and S. Cha, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1987, **36**, 2195.
21. F. N. M. Naguib, D. L. Levesque, E. C. Wang, R. P. Panzica and M. H. el Kouni, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1993, **46**, 1273.
22. N. M. Goudgaon, F. N. M. Naguib, M. H. el Kouni and R. F. Schinazi, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **36**, 4250.
23. N. M. Goudgaon and R. F. Schinazi, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 3305.
24. H. W. Barrett, I. Goodman and K. Dittmer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1753.